

Impact of Computer Utilization on Academic Achievement Among Senior Secondary School Students in Sokoto South Local Government

¹Hajara Abdulkadir & ²Nasiru Magaji

¹Department of Computer Science
Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, Sokoto, Nigeria
mamanummi203@gmail.com

²Department of Mathematics
Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, Sokoto, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study was intended to determine the effect of computer utilization on academic achievement of students. This study was guided by the following objectives; to examine the relationship between computer utilization and academic achievement of secondary school, students in Sokoto South Local Government to examine the effectiveness of computer usage in secondary school in Sokoto South. The study employed the survey design; questionnaires in addition to library research were applied in order to collect the data. Primary and secondary data sources were used and data was analyzed using the Likert Scale method which was presented in frequency table and percentage. The respondent under the study were 9200) teachers and students of some secondary schools in Sokoto South Sokoto State. The study finding revealed that compute usage is essentially for educational development. There is relationship between compute utilization and academic achievement of secondary school students. Computer utilization affects academic achievement of student in Sokoto South secondary school. The utilization of computer in academic activities enhance teaching and learning among secondary school students in Sokoto South Local Government. Computer utilization should therefore be encouraged in secondary education.

Keywords: academic achievement, computer utilization, students

INTRODUCTION

In the last two decades education institutions have invested heavily in information and communication technologies (ICT) particularly computer. The use of computer had a major impact in secondary school context, and in teaching and learning method (Ema and Ajayi, 2006).

According to Anyanwu (2003) they have faced two main difficulties on one hand, academic achievement is difficult to observe and there is still confusion about its definition. On the other hand, computer is an evolving technology and its effects are difficult to isolate from the environment.

There is no universal definition for students achievement. The standard approach focuses on achievement and curricula, how students understand the subject and obtain their certificate or their marks. However, a more extensive definition deals with competencies, skills and attitude learned through the education experience (Kamba, 2009).

The effect of computer utilization on learning is currently in relation to the internet to facilitate teaching and learning. Computers are the technologies used in conveying, collecting, processing and storage of data by electronic means, they provide an array of powerful tools that may help in transforming the present isolated teacher-centered and text bound classroom into rich, student-focused, interactive knowledge environment (Ogunsola, 2005).

To meet these challenges, secondary schools must embrace the new technologies and appropriate computer use for learning. The relationship between the use of computer and students' academic in secondary school is not clear, and there are contradictory results in the literature. Earlier, researches have failed to provide a clear consensus concerning the effect on students' achievement (Kamba, 2009).

Since students achievement is mainly explained by students' characteristics, educational environment and teachers characteristics, the use of computer may have an impact on these determinants and consequently the outcome of education. The differences observed in the achievement of students are thus more related to the differentiated impact of computer usage on the standard determinant (Valasidu and Bousiu, 2005).

The direct link between computer use and student's achievement has been the focus of extensive literature during the last two decades. Several studies have tried to explain the role and the added value of computer technologies in the classrooms and students' achievement. Since the internet revolution, there has been a shift in the literature that focuses more on the impact of online activities: use of internet, use of educative online platforms, digital devices, use of blog and wikis etc (Adel Ben Youssef, 2008).

Looking at the link between computer utilization and students' achievement seems now a day a misunderstanding of the role and nature of these technologies. In fact, since computer is General Purpose Technology (GPT), it needs to be specified in order to meet the need expressed by students and to be adopted to the local context and constraints (Antonelli, 2018; Youssef, 2008).

A variety of models of utilization can be identified by leading to some outcome. Computer utilization brings widened possibilities for the learning processes that are independent of place and space. Computer usage also allows more flexible and personalized learning. It offers new method of delivering subject at secondary education level. Taking advantages of these opportunities needs a profound change in the organization of the secondary education system (Ogunsola, 2015).

Statement of the Problem

For sometimes now the teaching and learning of computer in schools have increasingly become more challenging as a result of inadequate teaching-learning facilities. Many educators and stakeholder in the education sector have viewed with serious concern the performance of students in public secondary schools. Many researchers and educationists attributed the trend to the nonchalant attitude of students toward studies and the laissez-faire attitude of parents towards the educational pursuit of their wards. Worried by this ugly development, government, corporate bodies and well-meaning individuals have made concerted efforts to stimulate students' interest in learning, improve the performance and to make sure that the past glory of our educational system returns. These efforts have been in the area of providing basic teaching and learning materials, school infrastructural development, recruitment of qualified and competent teaches among others. All these efforts notwithstanding, the output has remained nothing to write home about. Moreover, most educators and researchers are of the opinion that with the introduction of computer to the teaching – learning process in schools, it situation will be overturned and the desired result would be achieved in view of the potential of computers in ensuring individualized instruction while believing that the incidence of students' failure in examination will be a thing of the past. It is against this background that the researcher is motivated to conduct a study on the effect of computer usage on academic achievement of secondary school students in Sokoto South Local Government Area (B.A. Buhari, 2015).

Research Objectives

The following are the research objectives of the study:

- i. To assess the extent of computers available in public secondary schools in Sokoto South Local Government Area.
- ii. To evaluate the extent of available computers utilized in public secondary schools in Sokoto South Local Government Area?

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

- i. To what extent are computers available in public secondary schools in Sokoto South Local Government Area?
- ii. To what extent are the available computers been utilized in public secondary schools in Sokoto South Local Government Area?

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: Computers available in public secondary schools in Sokoto South Local Government Area.

Ho₂: Computers been utilized in public secondary schools in Sokoto South Local Government Area

METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is the specification of procedure of collecting and analyzing the data necessary to solve the problems at hand. The purpose of this chapter is to provide data which should be adopted in order to attain the objective of the study. These are contained in the following such as research design, area of study, scope of the study, population of the study, sample and sampling technique, data collection procedure, instrument validity and reliability, administration and data analysis procedure

Research Design

This study adopts survey research design, because it is appropriate method of collecting data in which people are asked to answer a number of question (usually in the form of a questionnaire).

Area of Study

This study is conducted in some selected secondary schools in Sokoto South Local Government, Sokoto State.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consists of teachers and students of the following schools:

3. Sultan Bello Secondary School Sokoto South Sokoto State
4. Government Day Secondary School Gagi Area Sokoto South Sokoto State
5. Sultan Atiku Secondary School Sokoto South Sokoto State
6. Hafsatu Ahmadu Bello Secondary School Sokoto South Sokoto State.

As at the time of this study the population was (400). The break down shows the following:

Teachers	-	280
Students	-	120
Total number	-	400

Sample of the study

The selected members of the class or group (population) to be interviewed constitute the sample. The sample size of this research covers mainly the teachers and students of four major schools already aforementioned above. The sampling size purposely used for this study is determined by the Taro Yamani’s formula which is as follows:

$$Sample\ size\ (n) = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

N = The number of population in which sample is to be drawn

n = Sample size desired to be covered

e = Error estimate/ significance level, given as 0.05

i = Constant

Therefore to compute a sample size ‘n’ which shall be a representative of all confidence limit or 0.05 significant levels by using Taro Yamani’s formula

$$N = \frac{400}{1 + 400(0.05)^2}$$

$$N = \frac{400}{1 + 400(0.0025)}$$

$$N = \frac{400}{2.0} = 200$$

Due to some limitations in this study, this sample can be stratified as follows

Sultan Bello Sec. Sch.	-	50
Government Day Sec. Sch.	-	50
Sultan Atiku Sec. Sch.	-	50
Hafsatu Ahmadu Bello Sec. Sch.	-	50

Instrument for Data Collection

For this study, questionnaires were used to collect data from the sample respondents. The questionnaire is structure type and provides answers to the research questions.

This instruments is divided and limited into two section; section A and B. section A deals with the personal data of the respondents while section B contain research statement postulated in line with the research question, option or alternatives are provided for each respondent to pick or tick one of the option.

Reliability of Instrument

- e. The reliability of the instrument is established by carrying out pilot testing of the instrument at university model secondary school, Sokoto reliability index of 0.56 was established.
- f. Validity of the instrument. The instrument was validated by the researcher after careful observation.
- g. Procedure for data collection
Questionnaire were used to collect data in this study, the questionnaire is structured type and distributed to the sample respondent.

The questionnaire is divided into two sections; Section A and B. Section A deal with the personal data of the respondent while Section B contain research statement stated in line with the research question, option or alternatives are provided for each respondents to pick or tick some of the options.

Procedures for Data Analysis

In order to analyze the data, the researchers have distributed the questionnaire to the sample of two hundred respondents, where we make 200 samples into percentages, (200=100%) where I make 70=35%, 60=30%, 40=20%, 20=10% and 10=5%

- h. 35% of the respondents agreed
- i. 30% strongly agreed
- j. 20% undecided
- k. 10% disagreed
- l. 5% strongly disagreed

The following are some charts that represent the study

Series 1

The Bar Chart above represents the Study

The pie chart above represent the study

The pyramid chart that represent the study

Scoring of the research instrument

Since the research instrument used was the questionnaire, it was designed using the Likert Scale method.

The questionnaire was designed in the following ways

- m. Strongly Agreed (SA)
- n. Agreed (A)
- o. Undecided (U)
- p. Disagreed (D)
- q. Strongly Disagreed (SD)

RESULTS

This chapter deal with the presentation and analysis of the result obtained through questionnaires. The data gathered were presented according to the order in which they were arranged in the research question, simple percentage and Bar, pie and pyramid charts were used to analyze the demographic information of the respondents.

Demographic Data

Table 1: Distribution of Respondent by Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative percent
Valid male	100	50.0	50.0	50.0
Female	100	50.0	50.0	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, January 2022.

The table above shows the gender distribution of the 170 males and female teacher and 30 students (male and female) used this study. 100 respondents which represents 50.0% of the population are female

Table 2: Age range of respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative percent
Valid below 20years	30	15.0	15.0	15.0
21-30 years	70	35.0	35.0	50.0
31-40 years	60	30.0	30.0	80.0
41-50 years	20	10.0	10.0	90.0
51-60 years	20	10.0	10.0	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, January 2022.

Table 2 above shown the age grade of the respondents used for study

30 respondents which represents 15% of the population are below 20years, 70 respondents which represent 35.0% of the population are between 21-30 years. 60 respondents which represent 30% of the population are between 31-40years. 20 respondents which represent 10% of the population are between 41-50 years. 20 respondents which represent 10% of the population are between 51-60 years.

Table 3: Educational qualification of respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative percent
Valid JSLC	30	15.0	15.0	15.0
WAEC/SSCE/NECO	60	30.0	30.0	45.0
OND/NCE/HND/BSC	100	50.0	50.0	95.0
PGD/MSC/PHD	10	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, January 2022.

Table 3 above shows the educational qualification of respondents used for the study. 30 respondents representing 15% are JSLC holders. 60% respondents representing 30.0% percent are first WAEC/SSCE/NECO holders. 10 respondents representing 5% are PGD/MSC/PHD holders

Table 4: Marital Status of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative percent
Valid Single	70	35.0	35.0	35.0
Married	100	50.0	50.0	85.0
Divorced	15	7.5	7.5	95.0
Widowed	15	7.5	7.5	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, January 2022.

Table above shows the marital status of respondents used for the study. 70 respondents representing 35% are single, 100 respondents representing 50% are married, 15 respondents representing 7.5% are divorced and 15 respondents representing 7.5% are widowed.

Table 5: years of Experience

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative percent
Valid 0-2 years	60	30.0	30.0	30.0
3-5 years	100	50.0	50.0	80.0
6-11years	35	17.5	17.5	97.5
Above 12 years	5	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, January 2022.

Table 5 above shows the years of experience used for this study. 60 which represent 30% of the population have 0-2years experience. 100 which represent 50% of the population have 3-5years experience. 35 which

represent 17.5% of the population have 6-11 years of experience 5% which represent 2.5% of the population have over 12years of experience.

Summary

The study was done to determine the effect of computer utilization on academic achievement of secondary school students. Data were generated using questionnaire distributed to the respondent in the selected schools. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics tables that show frequency and percentage of the respondents. The results indicated that computer usage is essential for educational development in the study area. There is positive relationship between computer utilization and teaching and learning process. The study recommends that computer utilization among students and teachers should be encouraged for better academic achievement.

REFERENCES

- Adomi, E.E & Kpangpan, E. (2018). Application of ICTs in Nigerian Secondary Schools, *Library Philosophy and Practice*. 2(11): 211-219.
- Akinyemi, K. (2019). "Computer and Education" in Agun and Imogie (Eds). *Fundamental of Educational Technology*, Ibadan P. 203-217.
- Asika, N. (2019). *Research Methodology in the Behavioural Sciences*. Longman Nigeria Plc Nigeria. 32-44.
- Balagun, A. (2022). *Practice in the theory in the teaching of Geography in Nigerian secondary Schools*. Thesis presented to the Faculty of Education, University of Ibadan. Pp. 21-33.
- Boehim, G. (2018). *Learning to teach Geography in the Secondary Schools*. Routledge, Taylor and Francis Group: London. P. 41.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN (2020). *National Policy on Education Abuja: Federal Ministry of Education*.
- Hawkridge, D. Jaworski, I. and McMahan, H. (2021). "Computer in third world Schools." London Macmillan. Pp. 22-45.
- Howell, C. and Lundall, P. (2022). *Computer in Schools: National Survey of Information Communication Technology in South Africa*. Education Unit: University of Western Cape. P. 41.
- Isaacs, S. Broekman, I. and Mogale, T. (2018). Contextualizing Education in Africa: *The Role of ICT in Technologies for Development in Africa*: Vol.3: 19-29.